

Overlay Journals and the Path to Data Publication for the Meteorological Sciences

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Why publish data?

Scientific publication mainly focuses on the analysis, interpretation and conclusions drawn from a given dataset, as these are the information that can be easily published in hard copy text format with diagrams. Scrutinising the raw data that forms the dataset is more difficult, as datasets are usually stored in digital media, in a variety of (often proprietary or non-standard) formats.

This means that the peer-review process is generally only applied to the methodology and final conclusions of a piece of work, and not the underlying data itself. Yet for the conclusions to stand, the data must be of good quality. A process of data publication, involving peer-review of datasets would be of benefit to many sectors of the academic community.

Benefits of data publication

The **data scientists** who build, maintain, validate and collect the data for large databanks have to ensure that the data are of high quality and that the associated metadata and documentation are complete and understandable. This often represents a major task, which leaves little time for the analysis of the data required to produce a paper suitable for journal publication. Publishing a dataset in a data journal will provide academic credit to data scientists, and without diverting effort from their primary work on ensuring data quality.

A key driver for the **funding organisations** is obtaining the best possible science for their money. Running measurement campaigns is expensive, both in terms of equipment and time, so the more reuse that can be derived from a dataset, the better. Part of the submission process for publication in a data journal is uploading the dataset to a trusted repository where it will be backed up, properly archived and curated. As a result, the problems of data stored on obsolete media or suffering from bit-rot will be avoided, thereby minimising the need to repeat costly experiments.

Similarly, the peer-review process reassures the funder that the published dataset is of good quality and that the experiment was carried out appropriately.

When datasets have been peer-reviewed and published, it demonstrates to the **wider research community** that the datasets are reliable and complete, and therefore the data can be trusted. Publication of datasets will also be useful to **researchers outside the immediate field**, as going to a data journal for information about datasets will be a quick and convenient way of finding out not only what high-quality data are available, but also whom to contact about accessing them. This will encourage **inter-disciplinary collaboration**, and open up the user base not only for the datasets, but also the data journal and the underlying repositories.

Moreover, the availability of published datasets will make it easier to validate conclusions through the reanalysis of those datasets.

What is an overlay journal?

Overlay journals sit on top of, and make use of, the content stored in other pre-existing repositories. The overlay journal database itself consists of a number of overlay documents, which are structure documents created to annotate another resource with information on the quality of the resource. The overlay document has three basic elements:

1. metadata about the overlay document itself;
2. information about and from the quality process for which the document was constructed; and
3. basic metadata from the referenced resource to aid discovery and identification.

Information needed in an overlay document

The overlay documents can then be treated as any other documents in an electronic system, and they can provide added-value information about the resource they refer to, for example, a star-rating given by readers, or a series of review comments.

Overlay journals themselves do not actually store the datasets they reference, instead they simply store overlay documents about the datasets which contain links to the datasets.

The concept of overlay journals is not solely limited to data publication; they can be applied to other objects which can be stored in a repository, but which might not be so easy to reproduce in print, for instance, video or multimedia files. For example, an overlay journal might look at other journal-published and unpublished papers; its overlay document might allow users of the overlay journal to award star ratings to the paper to which it refers. The underlying technology for such an overlay journal remains the same.

The procedure for submitting a dataset for publication to an overlay journal is analogous to that of submitting a conventional paper to a print or on-line journal.

Survey results:

At the NCAS Conference in Bristol of 8-10 December 2008, conference delegates were invited to complete a survey to investigate the potential implications for the meteorological sciences should a **Journal of Meteorological Data** and an **Open Access Subject Repository** be created and operated.

Survey of users

- 85 delegates from 24 institutions responded to the survey (more than a third of the total number of delegates attending the conference).
- Respondents were mainly university-based scientists from the fields of atmospheric composition and chemistry, atmospheric physics, dynamical meteorology and climate science.
- 46% of respondents were less experienced scientists having less than three years experience of research work.
- 25% of respondents had more than 10 years experience.

Open-Access Repository for documents related to the meteorological sciences

The concept of the Open-Access Repository (the Repository) includes both a new subject-based repository and overlay mechanics to search and access it and other repositories.

- 70% of delegates rated at least one of the repository features as a great idea that they would use.
- 71% said the most appealing feature of the Repository was a "Single web site to search many repositories".
- 31% said they would use a "New repository for pre-print, post print, grey literature, podcasts, web-page archives, datasets and software". A further 65% said they might use this feature.
- 12-18% said they would use features such as "User rating of articles," "supplementary information e.g. videos, discussion group open forum," and "user comments and tags for items"
- 58% of respondents created grey literature, which might be stored in the new repository.
- 79% write papers for peer-reviewed journals.
- 19% use repositories as their most common method for getting the full text of articles (a further 28% use them occasionally to do so) and only 38% use institutional repositories to archive their articles.

It was concluded that the Repository could not become a single, comprehensive source of information for the meteorological sciences unless it attracts unprecedented volumes of deposits in its new repository, or inspires a step-change increase in archiving to existing repositories.

The survey results showed that about **two thirds** of researchers collaborate with non-meteorologists, and that about **three quarters** of them perceive that collaboration with non-meteorologists is increasing.

Journal of Meteorological Data

The concept behind the Journal of Meteorological Data is to extend the scientific discipline of peer review to data.

- 69% agreed that they would like to access data from an RMetS Journal.
- 67% agreed that they were more likely to deposit their data in a data centre if they can obtain academic credit through a data journal.
- Almost all respondents were users or creators of meteorological data of some kind. Data from experimental campaigns was more commonly used and created by these NCAS delegates than data from General Circulation Models, other numerical models, operational systems, and instrument and observing facilities.
- The evidence of increasing collaboration suggests an emerging market for provision of meteorological data to non-meteorologists.
- 91% of respondents had never heard of the only existing data journal in this area, which is aimed at all environmental sciences.
- 93% of respondents have heard of Atmospheric Science Letters, the RMetS on-line journal.